

INTEGRATION OF DIFFERENT KERNELS FOR NEURO FUZZY CONCEPT USING FOR MRI MEDICAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION

*A Report Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of
POST DOCTORAL FELLOW*

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OCTOBER- 2022

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements.

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Certificate

This is to certify that the study entitled “**DESIGN AND INTEGRATION OF DIFFERENT KERNELS FOR FUZZY C-MEANS ALGORITHM USED FOR MRI MEDICAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION**” submitted by **Dr.NOOKALA VENU** to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by his under my supervision and guidance. The content of the report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to express my profound sense of gratitude to my supervising teacher, **Dr.Rajanna G.S**, Department of Electronics and communication Engineering, Srinivas university, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore without whose skilful guidance expert advice, this report would not have appeared in the present form, I am deeply indebted to him for the earnest he had shown in me and in my academic effort.

I express my gratitude to our honorable Vice-Chancellor, **Dr.P.S.Aithal** for providing all the facilities in the Srinivas University and helping me in the completion of my research work successfully.

I acknowledge my sincere thanks to **Dr. Praveen B M**, Research Director, Srinivas University, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore for holding me to a high research standard and enforcing for good research result.

It is a great pleasure for me to express my sincere thanks to **Dr. A.Rajendra Prasad Reddy**, Chairman, Balaji Group of Institutions, Narsampet, Warangal, Telangana.

I am indebted to convey my thanks to **Dr.V.S.Hariharan**, Principal, Balaji Institute of Technology and Science, Narsampet, Warangal, Telangana for his constant encouragement in the completion of my research work.

I express my deepest gratitude to **Mr.S.Suresh**, Administrative fficer, Balaji Institute of Technology and Science, Narsampet, Warangal, Telangana.

I express my heartfelt thanks to all Teaching and Non-Teaching Faculty, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Balaji Institute of Technology and Science, Narsampet, Warangal, Telangana.

I finally offer this humble piece of work to the Holy feet of **Lord Sri Venkateswara** and his Holy spouse **Padmavathammavaru**.

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SYNOPSIS

INTEGRATION OF DIFFERENT KERNELS FOR NEURO FUZZY CONCEPT USING FOR MRI MEDICAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION

IINTRODUCTION

Image segmentation is one of the first and most important tasks in image analysis and computer vision. In the literature, various methods have been proposed for object segmentation and feature extraction. However, the design of robust and efficient segmentation algorithms is still a very challenging research topic, due to the variety and complexity of images. Image segmentation is defined as the partitioning of an image into non overlapped, consistent regions which are homogeneous in respect to some characteristics such as intensity, color, tone, texture, etc. The image segmentation can be divided into four categories: thresholding, clustering, edge detection and region extraction.

In this report, a clustering method for image segmentation is considered. Image segmentation is to partition image to different regions based on given criteria for future process. Medical image segmentation is a key task in many medical applications. There are lots of methods for automatic and semi automatic image segmentation, though, most of them fail in unknown noise, poor image contrast, and weak boundaries that are usual in medical images. Medical images mostly contain complicated structures and their precise segmentation is necessary for clinical diagnosis.

An interesting source of images is the medical field. Here, imaging modalities such as CT (Computed Tomography), MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), PET (Positron Emission Tomography) etc. generate a huge amount of image information. Not only does the size and resolution of the images grow with improved technology, also the number of dimensions increase.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Clustering is a process for classifying objects or patterns in such a way that samples of the same cluster are more similar to one another than samples belonging to

different clusters. There are two main clustering strategies: the hard clustering scheme and the fuzzy clustering scheme.

Ahmed et al. (1997) have proposed a system to segment and label CT/MRI brain slices using feature extraction and unsupervised clustering is presented. Each volume element voxel is assigned a feature pattern consisting of a scaled family of differential geometrical invariant features. The invariant feature pattern is then assigned to a specific region using a two-stage neural network system.

Ahmed et al. (2002) proposed FCM_S where the objective function of the classical FCM is modified in order to compensate the intensity inhomogeneity and allow the labeling of a pixel to be influenced by the labels in its immediate neighborhood. One of the disadvantages of FCM_S is that the neighborhood labeling is computed in each iteration step, something that is very time-consuming.

Xue et al. (2003) have proposed the integrated method of the adaptive enhancement for an unsupervised global-to-local segmentation of brain tissues in three-dimensional (3-D) MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) images. Three brain tissues are of interest: CSF (Cerebro Spinal Fluid), GM (Gray Matter), WM (White Matter). Firstly, they de-noise the images using a newly proposed versatile wavelet-based filter, and segment the images with minimum error global thresholding. Subsequently, we combine a spatial-feature-based FCM (Fuzzy C-Means) clustering with 3-D clustering-result weighted median and average filters, so as to further achieve a locally adaptive enhancement and segmentation. This integrated strategy yields a robust and accurate segmentation, particularly in noisy images. The performance of the proposed method is validated by four indices on MRI brain phantom images and on real MRI images.

Chen and Zhang (2004) tried to propose FCM_S1 and FCM_S2, two variants of FCM_S algorithm in order to reduce the computational time. These two algorithms introduced the extra mean and median-filtered image, respectively, which can be computed in advance, to replace the neighborhood term of FCM_S. Thus, the execution times of both FCM_S1 and FCM_S2 are considerably reduced. Further they have improved the FCM_S objective function to more likely reveal inherent non-Euclidean structures in data and more robustness to noise. Then they had replaced the Euclidean distance by a kernel-induced distance and proposed kernel versions of FCM with spatial

constraints, called KFCM_S1 and KFCM_S2 (Chen and Zhang (2004)). However, the main drawback of FCM_S and its variants FCM_S1 and FCM_S2 and KFCM_S1 and KFCM_S2 is that their parameters heavily affect the final clustering results.

Kannan et al. (2011) have tried the hyper tangent FCM (HTFCM) based image segmentation for breast images. They have used the hyper tangent function as objective function in place of original Euclidean distance on feature space.

The proposed GKFCM algorithm becomes a generalized type of FCM, KFCM_S1 and KFCM_S2 algorithms and presents with more efficiency and robustness. Chen et al. (2011) have used the multiple-kernel fuzzy C-means (FCM) (MKFCM) for image-segmentation problems. They have used the linear combination of multiple kernels as composite kernel.

Szilagyi et al. (2013).Cai et al. (2007) suggested the fast generalized FCM algorithm (FGFCM) which incorporates the spatial information, the intensity of the local pixel neighborhood and the number of gray levels in an image. This algorithm forms a nonlinearly-weighted sum image from both original image and its local spatial and gray level neighborhood. The computational time of FGFCM is very small, since clustering is performed on the basis of the gray level histogram. The quality of the segmented image is well enhanced (Cai et al. (2007)). Yang and Tsai (2008) have tried the Gaussian kernel based FCM (GKFCM) for medical image segmentation.

Szilagyi et al. (2013) come up with a proposal of the enhanced FCM (EnFCM) algorithm to accelerate the image segmentation process. The structure of the EnFCM is different from that of FCM_S and its variants. First, a linearly-weighted sum image is formed from both original image and each pixel's local neighborhood average gray level. Then clustering is performed on the basis of the gray level histogram instead of pixels of the summed image. Since, the number of gray levels in an image is generally much smaller than the number of its pixels, the computational time of EnFCM algorithm is reduced, while the quality of the segmented image is comparable to that of FCM_S.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Based on the above discussion and the relevant literature reviewed on medical image segmentation strategy, the research work is carried out to achieve the following main objectives.

- A novel and efficient segmentation algorithm based on the clustering required (Fuzzy c-means algorithm).
- The design and integration of different kernels are needed for better segmentation performance.
- Integration of one or more kernels (Multi-Kernels) can improve the medical image segmentation performance.
- The proposed segmentation algorithm should be robust for different noise conditions.
- The convergence of the fuzzy c-means algorithm should be in reasonable number of iterations.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Based on the literature review and objectives, current research work concentrated on the design and integration of different kernels for fuzzy c-means algorithm for medical image segmentation. In this work, five new approaches are proposed for medical image segmentation application. The proposed five approaches are discussed in the following paragraphs.

The performance of the proposed methods is tested under different noise conditions different images (normal and abnormal) and also verified the convergence of the algorithm in terms of number of iterations.

CONCLUSION

The design of different types of kernels for image segmentation is important and challenging task in medical imaging application. Hence, the current research work concentrated on the design and integration of different kernels for fuzzy c-means algorithm for medical image segmentation.

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1.1 INTRODUCTION:

1.1.1 Integration of Different Kernels for Neuro fuzzy

Based on fuzzy set theory, Lofti Zadeh (1969), established the concept of fuzzy logic as a new way to characterize non-probabilistic uncertainty in the early 1960s. More than a century after its creation, there are numerous applications of fuzzy logic, including fuzzy reasoning, fuzzy models of reality, inference, expert systems and associative memories are only few of the terminology used to describe fuzzy inference systems. As mentioned, FIS is made up of three basic parts an inference engine that uses rules and given facts to form conclusions, a database of fuzzy membership functions and fuzzy rules. In order to represent the qualitative characteristics of human reasoning without the need for a precise mathematical model, fuzzy if-then rules can be used. It is possible to create the fuzzy rule foundation for FIS by using a fuzzy modeling methodology or by working with domain experts directly, however this is an error-prone and time-consuming method of producing the rules. If-then logic is used to express the system's behavior in terms of quantifiable attributes in fuzzy modeling, or fuzzy identification. For the estimate of dynamic fuzzy systems, Takagi et al. (1985) were the first to properly investigate it as an effective technique, even though it had been examined previously. Using fuzzy modeling, it can figure out how many fuzzy rules there are in the rule base and what the membership function parameter values are for each of them. Control, prediction, and other applications are currently using fuzzy modeling to identify fuzzy models based on observed input and output datasets. Models that use fuzzy logic instead of black box methods like neural networks may be able to highlight the connections between the model's various variables [1]. Data obtained from observable input and output data can be combined with prior expert knowledge using fuzzy modeling techniques. In contrast, only through optimization and adaptive approaches can a stand-alone FIS learn and be improved. The ANFIS model, proposed by Jang (1995), refers to inference systems and neural networks. Because of their ability to learn and link, neuronal networks mimic the thinking process of humans by applying fuzzy logic based on fuzzy principles. It is possible to divide the data set into clusters using clustering and FCM clustering, two methods for capturing trends in the data sets. There are various ways in which the fuzzy if-then rules are constructed, and the final rule base is fine-tuned from the original rule base.

The brain is the largest and most complicated organ in the human body. It is responsible for all of the world's ideas, actions, memories, senses and comprehension. There is a complicated

network of connections between brain cells each neuron can communicate with thousands of other neurons. Every second there are quite a few associations. Memories are accumulated, habits are learned, and personalities are shaped in these changing relationships by reinforcing certain patterns of brain activity while losing others. The nervous system is made up of the brain, nerves, and spinal cord. GM, WM, and CSF make up the human brain [2]. The nerve cells are encased in grey matter. Neurotransmitters are nerve cells and molecules that aid in the communication of various regions of the body. Tumors, convulsions, migraines, and other issues can all affect how the brain works. Epilepsy is a type of epilepsy in which a person has a series of seizures throughout time. Seizures are periods of disturbed brain activity that result in changes in concentration or activity. Figures 1 to 3 depict the human brain's structure, the cortex's structure and the nervous system's structure, respectively.

Fig.1.1: Structure of the Human Brain

Fig.1.2: Structure of Cortex

Fig.1.3: The Nervous System in Brain

1.2 MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

Since the first successful Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) experiments in 1946, various scientists have worked for more than half a century to develop MRI into the technology that it is today [7-8]. MRI has gradually become one of the most popular imaging modalities for observing bodily structures, as it allows physicians to see dissimilarities between soft tissues with incredible acuity. MRI is a type of imaging that is essentially non-invasive and does not

use ionizing radiation.

CT scan and MRI provide greater information on bodily structures in certain cases. An MRI, unlike other imaging methods, creates digital images. Blood vessels, bones, the pelvis, joints, and the belly are all included in this category. It is used to detect issues such as tumors, injuries, bleeding, blood vessel diseases, and infection. Furthermore, contrast chemicals may be used at some point during an MRI to make aberrant tissue more visible. It's also often used in studies to assess brain shape and function. The patient lies within a huge hollow cylindrical magnet and is subjected to a powerful stable magnetic field during an MRI treatment, as shown in Figure 4. Several atoms in the body sections being scanned respond to different magnetic field frequencies [11-12]. With MRI, you can see the oscillations of hydrogen atoms everywhere around an item that's moving around. Consequently, the proton nucleus can be thought of as possessing a small magnetic field.

Fig.1.4: MRI Scanner

There are background magnetic fields that align hydrogen atoms in the tissue being studied in an MRI situation. This second field resonates and aligns with the hydrogen atoms at specific pulse rates [13-15]. On and off cycles of a second magnetic field, with a different orientation than the background field are performed many times per second. When the second field is switched off, all of the atoms that had been aligned with it revert to the background field. A signal can be taken up and converted into a picture by swinging back simultaneously.

- **The major benefits of MRI system are as follows:**
 - ✓ It has a lot of potential in terms of soft tissue imaging.
 - ✓ It has a high resolution of 1mm cubic voxels.

- ✓ It has a higher signal to noise ratio, and
- ✓ Multi channel pictures with unequal contrast may be achieved with the help of varied pulse sequences; this can be exploited further for segmenting and categorizing distinct structures.

1.3 Need for Human Brain Magnetic Resonance Imaging Segmentation

The segmentation of GM, WM, and CSF tissues on MRI images is critical in epilepsy research and clinical diagnosis. In the future, it will be critical that the segmentation method aids in the detection of epileptic tissue [16].

Although manual segmentation by qualified professionals is still preferable to automatic approaches in terms of quality, it does have two downsides. The first disadvantage is that creating human or semi-automated segmentations takes a long time, with higher accuracies on more finely defined volumes necessitating more effort from medical professionals [17].

The second issue with manual and semiautomatic segmentation is that it is prone to differences in segmentation between observers as well as within the same observer. Manual segmentation has no trust in monitoring epilepsy tissue during the patient follow-up procedure, and automatic approaches with appropriate accuracy would be highly desirable for their ability to execute high-throughput segmentation [18].

Automatic approaches, on the other hand, would be favorable because they are not prone to this volatility, making it easier to judge the significance of changes in Gray Matter tissue. Accurate automatic segmentation methods have the potential to reduce the variability and raise the consistency of other measures and protocols, such as the quantification of edoema or necrosis, in addition to locating epileptic sources inside the brain [19].

Automatic segmentation may also open the door to new applications, such as efficient content-based picture retrieval in huge medical databases. This could allow clinicians to search past data for similar images based on epileptic tissue location, grade, size, augmentation, and amount of edoema, growth patterns, and other characteristics [20].

This information, in addition to being a great research tool for exploring patterns in previous data, could assist therapists in making judgments. Similarly, to improve epilepsy detection, an effective segmentation method could be employed in conjunction with pertinent characteristics and machine learning algorithms [21].

Because of the benefits of automatic segmentation mentioned above, it has become a necessary concern for clinicians. Other than PET and CT pictures, MRI images can benefit

from artificial segmentation. One of the most prominent diagnostic procedures used to predict epilepsy in patients is MRI [21].

Due to a scarcity of radiologists and the high amount of MRI scan images that must be evaluated, labor-intensive, expensive, and erroneous prediction may be the result. As a result, there is a need to develop an effective prediction model for correctly diagnosing epilepsy and accurately predicting its kind [21].

1.4 AUTOMATED SEGMENTATION FOR HUMAN BRAIN MRI

To segment epileptic tissue more correctly, an automated segmentation system for epilepsy via MRI is critical. To segment tissues, preprocessing and segmentation work is done on MRI images in general [22].

This study is primarily concerned with segmentation using a preprocessing task. In order to accurately separate undesirable regions in MRI, preprocessing techniques are first used to increase picture quality and remove disturbances. The segmentation is used to segment cerebral tissues from MRI brain images after preprocessing. The appearance of segmented tissues contains some information that will be important in further epilepsy surgery identification [12].

The most visible level of medical image processing is the image filtering and enhancement stage. When the image is distorted by numerous sounds, the filtering strategy has been proven to be the best [25].

If the noise level is low, normal filters may be effective; but, if the noise level is excessive, normal filters will be ineffective [29].

In this instance, using a mix of filters to improve the image's quality is essential. This level of pre-processing is used to reduce image noise, emphasize critical areas, and display visible parts of digital images [6].

1.4.1 Segmentation

Images can be captured in a continuous domain, such as on X-ray film, or in a discrete region, such as in an MRI scan. A pixel is the location of each measurement in a 2-D discrete image. If the image's domain is defined with 'I,' denoting matrix representation, the challenge remains to find a situation where in union of sets equals' full image.

Consequently $I = \bigcup_{k=1}^K S_k$ where $\bigcap S_j$ for $k \neq j$, S_k and each S_k is connected.

A segmentation approach should, in theory, discover those sets in the image that correspond to discrete anatomical structures or regions of interest.

When the requirement that regions be connected is removed, pixel categorization is used to determine the sets, and the sets themselves are referred to as classes.

In medical imaging, pixel classification, rather than traditional segmentation, is frequently a desirable goal, especially when disjointed sections belonging to the same tissue class need to be detected.

From an MRI of the brain, different types of segmentations can be used to locate epileptic episodes. These segmentations offer a number of benefits and drawbacks [6].

1.5 Architecture Flow Diagram

Fig. 5: Work Flow Diagram of the Overall Research Work

1.6 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Medical image processing of coherent echo signals can be used in some more approaches prior to image formation and some of the images are dangling from clip, so they may cause noise. The resolution and contrast enhancement stages are included in the enhancement step. These are utilized for noise suppression and spectral parameter imaging [29-30]. The medical image is then turned into a normal image that is free of noise, film artifacts, and labeling. Numerous strategies have been used in noise reduction investigations. However, removing irrelevant background elements remains tough. This challenge is tackled by primarily using skull stripping for image improvement. The most frequent techniques are region growth and mathematical morphology.

There are no algorithms that consistently generate excellent results for all types of MRI brain pictures. As a result, precise segmentation across the entire field of view is a serious issue, but verification of the results during the segmentation process is also a challenge [29-30].

1.7 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

This research work has covered information related to various existing FCM algorithms for MRI for medical image segmentation. This research work is carried out with the following broad objectives.

- To study the existing algorithm.
- To analyze the data related to improve the accuracy of the existing HTFCM Algorithm.
- To identify the advantages, disadvantages and issues if any with existing algorithm.
- To propose the HGFCM Algorithm for Neuro fuzzy based Concept using for MRI Medical Image Segmentation.
- To identify the improvement of classification, number of iterations.

1.8. METHODOLOGY:

1.8.1 Fuzzy C-means Algorithm

A mechanism to represent and manipulate uncertainty within an image is provided by a fuzzy set theoretic model. Adequate number of methods for accessible for image segmentation. Thus proper clustering technique called fuzzy-c means. This is used for obtaining excellent results in image region clustering algorithms. It is considered as a fuzzy c-means algorithm depends upon minimization of the function and each criterion.

If image pixels are represented as $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. FCM establishes the clustering by Iteratively reducing the objective function given in Eq. (1).

Objective function:

$$O_m(U, C) = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m D^2(x_j, C_i) \quad (1)$$

Constraint:

$$\sum_{i=1}^c U_{ij} = 1; \quad \forall j \quad (2)$$

Where, U_{ij} is membership of the j^{th} data in the i^{th} cluster C_i , m is fuzziness of the system ($m=2$) and D is the separation between pixel & cluster center .

Figure 6 describes the flowchart of FCM. Steps implemented are also provided.

Algorithm

Input: Raw image; Output: Segmented image;

- Adjust the cluster centers C_i ($c = 3$ clusters).
- The distance D between the cluster center and pixel by using Eq. (3). has to be calculated.

$$D^2(x_j, C_i) = \|x_j - C_i\|^2 \quad (3)$$

- The membership values by using Eq. (4).has to be calculated.

$$U_{ij} = \frac{(D(x_j, C_i))^{-1/(m-1)}}{\sum_{k=1}^c (D(x_j, C_k))^{-1/(m-1)}} \quad (4)$$

- The cluster centers using Eq. (5).has to be updated

$$C_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m} \quad (5)$$

- The commencement of iterative process :
 1. The membership values U_{ij} by using Eq. (4).has to be calculated
 2. Thee the cluster centers C_i by using Eq. (5).has to be updated
 3. The distance D using Eq. (3).has to be calculated
 4. If $|C_{\text{new}} - C_{\text{old}}| > \xi$; ($\xi = 0.001$) then go to step1

5. Otherwise stop:

- Allot each pixel to a specific cluster where the membership is maximum.

Fig. 1.6: FCM flowchart

1.8.2 Integration of Gaussian Kernels & Hyperbolic Tangent for FCM (HGFCM)

The concepts presented in HTFCM and GKFCM are used HGFCM_S1 and HGFCM_S2[36]. Furnished bellow.

$$H(x_j, C_i) = 1 - \tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \quad (6)$$

Where, σ^2 is denoted as a defined function.

The performance of the segmentation algorithm varies with the σ^2 values. Hence, it is required to fix need to fix the appropriate value for σ^2 .

The value of σ^2 with the variance of the surrounding P neighbors of radius R form the center pixel x_j .

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_{j=1}^P \|x_j - \bar{x}\| / P \quad (7)$$

Where, $\bar{x} = \sum_{j=1}^P x_j / P$.

The objective function which is used in this paper for HGFCM_S1 and HGFCM_S2 are provided bellow.

$$O_m^H(U, C) = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m \tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) + \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n \eta_i U_{ij}^m \tanh(-\|\bar{x}_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \quad (8)$$

$$U_{ij} = \frac{\left(\left(\tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) + \eta_i \left(1 - \tanh(-\|\bar{x}_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) \right)^{-1/(m-1)}}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\left(\tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) + \eta_i \left(\tanh(-\|\bar{x}_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) \right)^{-1/(m-1)}}; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, C \quad (9)$$

$$C_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m \left(\left(1 - \tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) x_j + \eta_i \left(1 - \tanh(-\|\bar{x}_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) \bar{x}_j \right)}{\sum_{j=1}^n U_{ij}^m \left(\left(1 - \tanh(-\|x_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) + \eta_i \left(1 - \tanh(-\|\bar{x}_j - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right) \right)}; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, C \quad (10)$$

$$\eta_i = \frac{\min_{i' \neq i} \left(\tanh(-\|C_{i'} - C_i\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right)}{\max_k \left(\tanh(-\|C_k - C_x\|^2 / \sigma^2) \right)}; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, C \quad (11)$$

Where, $\bar{x}_j$ is the median for HGFCM_S2 and mean for HGFCM_S1.

Algorithm

Input: Raw image; Output: Segmented image;

- The cluster centers C_i ($c = 3$ clusters).has to be updated
- The membership values by using Eq. (9).has to be calculated
- The cluster centers using Eq. (10).has to be updated
- The iterative process starts:
 1. The membership values U_{ij} by using Eq. (9).has to be calculated
 2. The cluster centers C_i by using Eq. (10).has to be updated
 3. If $|C_{new} - C_{old}| > \xi$; ($\xi = 0.001$) then go to step1
 4. Else stop
- 5. Allot each pixel to a specific cluster where the membership is maximum.

1.8.3 Segmentation Accuracy / Score

Segmentation accuracy score is treated for evaluation measure in this research paper.

In this paper, segmentation accuracy/score as one of the evaluation measures. The score (S_{ik}) calculation [31] is done as per following equations.

$$Score(S_{ik}) = \frac{A_k \cap A_{refk}}{A_k \cup A_{refk}} \quad (12)$$

Where set of pixels pertaining to the k^{th} class found by the i^{th} algorithm are represented by A_{ik} and A_{refk} represents the k^{th} class in the original segmented image.

Number of iterations and execution time required for the convergence of algorithm are explained.

1.8.4 MRI Dataset

The OASIS is a series of MRI dataset t is readily available for analysis. This dataset comprise of a cross-sectional collection of 602 subjects aged 16 to 99 years. The MRI acquisition details are given in Table 1. The evaluation of the proposed method in terms of score, NI and time. Figure 7 display the selected image for experimentation.

Table 1.1: MRI data acquisition details

Sequence	Gradient Eco-planner
TR (msec)	27
TE (msec)	24
Flip angle (o)	70
TI (msec)	25
TD (msec)	210
Orientation	Sagittal
Thickness, gap (mm)	1.25, 0
Resolution (pixels)	64×64

Fig. 1.7: Selected image used for experiment

1.9 RELATED WORK:

A lot of researches have recently tackled the challenge of fuzzy model identification using data clustering methods. For this reason, kernel methods have been used in conjunction with other traditional clustering algorithms in multiple research.

Yang et al. (2008) suggested a new dual kernel-based procedure for fuzzy modeling of a Takagi-Sugeno method. For splitting data into distinct clusters, the authors employed a standard FCM technique. The support vectors inside each cluster were then located using a kernel function that was unconventional of the parameter collection problem.

The study's experimental findings revealed that the strategy produced a fuzzy model with a compact structure and strong generalization capabilities. The system's performance was also unaffected by the initial cluster number required in FCM.

For fuzzy rule extraction, a kernel-density gradient estimation technique was introduced. Clustering based on the kernel density estimation was utilized by the authors. The rule base was built using the cluster centers obtained from clustering. The technique was based on the idea that each cluster can be based on the local maximum of a kernel compute of a probability density concern for m-dimensional data. However, instead of using the density function, the authors employed the density function's gradient to identify cluster centers. This approach's neuro-fuzzy system was tested for non-linear function estimate and controller fusion.

With the use of an iterative feature vector selection (FVS) using the kernel approach, the Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model's parameter values and fuzzy rule count were discovered. To obtain a basis of data space termed characteristic vector into the feature space, the kernel-based FVS technique was utilized. In the antecedent section of the fuzzy rule, this characteristic vector was used as the centre of a membership justification.

The proposed fuzzy system was used to model a two-input non-linear function, demonstrating its usefulness in non-linear system modeling. A new fuzzy system modeling method based on kernel machines was proposed. All of these computers were used to build the kernel machine. Changes in parameter values or the transformation matrix of kernel function were the work's main contribution to reducing fuzzy rules by gradient descent. Using the approach to solve a variety of real-world, non-linear situations showed that it worked.

Fuzzy rule-based models have been shown in nearly all earlier research articles to benefit from the use of kernel techniques; however, no one has ever investigated the use of the KSC and KFCM kernel methods for the popular ANFIS model, which is the focus of this work [32].

1.10. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Experiments on two brain MRIs were undertaken to establish the efficiency of the suggested algorithm [22-23]. The research includes comparing the suggested algorithm's Score, NI and Time on the OASIS-MRI data set with many current FCM variant Techniques (CT).

Fig.1.8: Comparison of proposed techniques (HGFCM_S1 and HGFCM_S2) with other existing methods (GKFCM_S1, GKFCM_S2 and HTFCM) in terms of three segmented clusters. The original image (*figure 7*) is corrupted with 5% of Gaussian noise.

Table 1.2: Comparison of HGFCM_S1 and HGFCM_S2 Algorithms in terms of Score at different Gaussian Noise.

Method	Gaussian Noise (%)											
	5%			10%			15%			20%		
	Cl-1	Cl-2	Cl-3	Cl-1	Cl-2	Cl-3	Cl-1	Cl-2	Cl-3	Cl-1	Cl-2	Cl-3
GKFCM-S1	0.31	0.54	0.80	0.44	0.51	0.75	0.49	0.51	0.72	0.43	0.48	0.72
GKFCM-S2	0.44	0.61	0.81	0.48	0.54	0.77	0.50	0.55	0.74	0.44	0.49	0.74
HTFCM	0.49	0.65	0.83	0.51	0.55	0.79	0.54	0.59	0.77	0.46	0.51	0.76
HGFCM-S1	0.69	0.72	0.87	0.60	0.74	0.84	0.55	0.71	0.82	0.52	0.68	0.78
HGFCM-S2	0.72	0.74	0.89	0.62	0.76	0.85	0.58	0.74	0.83	0.54	0.69	0.79

Table 1.3: Comparison of various methods in terms of number of iterations and execution time at different Gaussian noise on Image (*figure 7*).

NI: Number of iterations; TM: Execution Time (Sec.)

Method	Gaussian Noise							
	5%		10%		15%		20%	
	NI	TM	NI	TM	NI	TM	NI	TM
GKFCM-S1	54	0.69	46	0.71	41	0.60	44	0.64
GKFCM-S2	44	0.67	53	0.69	33	0.62	41	0.67
HTFCM	32	0.35	23	0.52	30	0.55	34	0.44
HGFCM-S1	14	0.24	14	0.31	16	0.40	24	0.40
HGFCM-S2	13	0.31	13	0.30	13	0.31	26	0.33

1.10.1 Experimental Results with Gaussian Noise

Figure 8 illustrates the individual cluster segmentation results of various techniques with the 5% Gaussian noise on *Image (figure 7)* of OASIS-MRI dataset. The performance of the proposed methods (HGFCM_S1 and HGFCM_S2) is compared with the GKFCM_S1, GKFCM_S2 and HGFCM. Table 2 and Table 3 indicate the segmentation performance of various methods with different levels of Gaussian noise in terms of score on *image (figure 7)* respectively. Table 2 and Table 3 describe the performance of the various methods in terms NI and TM on *Image (figure 7)*. From, Figure 8 and Tables 2 and 3, it explicit that the proposed segmentation algorithms outperform the existing algorithms in terms of Score, NI and TM.

1.11 CONCLUSIONS:

Two new image segmentation algorithms (HGFCM_S2 and HGFCM_S1) are proposed. Both algorithms improve the performance while requiring less processing. Segmentation methods were developed that took into account the morphological and pathological distinctions between medullablastoma and astrocytoma in order to improve efficiency and segmentation accuracy. Gaussian kernels are used in conjunction with an integrated hyperbolic tangent function. The proposed method is used to improve brain MRI images influenced by Gaussian noise. When compared to conventional FCM-based picture segmentation algorithms, the proposed method is more stable under a wide range of sounds. K-Means and the FCM approach are used to segment the brain cerebral tissues utilizing clustering segmentation algorithms. FCM reduces OvS, InS, and UnS rate in GM, WM, and CSF tissues when compared to K-Means. The segmentation of cerebral tissues from noisy and denoised MRI

brain images is improved using optimized clustering segmentation, which is combined with FCM. Firefly Algorithm lowered segmentation metrics in GM, WM, and CSF tissues when compared to Genetic Algorithm. To improve the segmentation of cerebral tissues from noisy and denoised MRI brain images, it is suggested a random-based optimal clustering segmentation combined with FCM. LFFAFCM reduced the assessment metrics in GM, WM, and CSF tissues significantly when compared to CFAFCM.

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2.1 INTRODUCTION:

The use of technology to aid in the computation of medical images has become important as their size and number have grown [1]. In particular, image segmentation techniques are used in a variety of biomedical imaging applications such as tissue diagnosis, volume measurement, computer-integrated surgery and anatomical structure studies, to delineate anatomical structures and other regions of interest. Image segmentation is traditionally defined as the division of an image into mutually exclusive subsets constituent sections that are uniform in terms of certain criteria like brightness or texture. Due to the obvious benefits of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) over conventional diagnostic imaging [2], the majority of medical image segmentation research focuses on its application to MR pictures, and there are numerous approaches for MR image segmentation [2-6]. Fuzzy segmentation approaches, for example, have significant advantages over hard segmentation methods in that they can retain significantly additional data from the source image [3]. The fuzzy C-means (FCM) method [7], in instance, assigns images to fuzzy clusters lacking labels. Despite hard approaches, which require pixels to belong to only one class, FCM permits images to be users of several clusters with varied degrees of membership. FCM has lately become popular in MR image segmentation scenarios because to its increased flexibility. Furthermore, due to in homogeneity is temporal intensity, in an MR image, caused either by radio-frequency coil. The traditional FCM algorithm is based on intensity. Also when progressed, it has shown to be a concern. Semi and multi-channel approaches [2] Techniques are being used. In order to cope against non-uniformity. Several algorithms have now been presented to solve this problem by incorporating corrective procedures prior to segmentation by modeling the imagery as the [4,5] or by modeling the image as the a combination of a main image or a smoothly changing gradient [2,6] multiplication area Several researchers have been working on this topic recently have included spatial data into the first. For further divide the image, use the Morphological operations. [6,8-10]. Tolia and Panas [8] suggested a fuzzy classification system a rule-based approach for enforcing spatial consistency. They employed a tiny sample size in FCM and another paper [9] favorable constant to change the composition of a group .In a 3* 3 window, the centre pixel Pham and colleagues [6] added a multipliers field to the FCM algorithm's optimization problem, which contains the image's first- and second-order knowledge. Likewise, Ahmed et al. [11] suggested another algorithm for compensating for contrast enhancement or labeling pixels by taking into account its near

surroundings. Phan [12] suggested a new strategy that penalizes the FCM objective function to control the behavior of a membership functions, comparable to regularization and Markov random field (MRF) theoretical methods. In contemporary machine learning research, however, there has been a tendency to use the 'kernel technique' to develop a linear version of a linear algorithm, such as SVM [13-15], KPCA [16], and KFD [17]. Unsupervised clustering has also been used with this 'kernel technique' [18-20]. Even so, one disadvantage of such kernel clustering algorithms that use the some double representation for clustering working prototype (that really is, every design is developed as just a sequential total amount of the after data - set elements, and thus the variables to just be optimized aren't any longer initial reproductions though - and linear fashion coefficients) is whether the grouping prototypes are located in a strong subspace, and thus the clusters lack simple and user-friendly explanations, a new kernel zed fuzzy C-means (KFCM) technique is proposed in the paper and subsequently applied to MR segmentation. It is achieved by substituting a kernel-induced distance for the initial Euclidean distance inside the FCM method [30], as well as a novel spatial penalty. This punishment term serves as a ReLU, and the rate was similar with it ranges from nougat to one. It is demonstrated. That the suggested technique outperforms traditional algorithms like FCM in segmenting simulated or real MR images damaged by noise and other abnormalities.

2.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

The challenge is aimed at making use of machine learning and artificial intelligence(AI) in interpreting different Kernels for Neuron fuzzy based dataset. The dataset made available to participants is on the Scripts of the different Kernels for Neuron fuzzy Based, Wikipedia data about the MRI Medical Image Segmentation and Images in the different Kernels for Neuron fuzzy. In this paper, it is aimed at imparting the ability to get rid of biases in a machine or an AI system. Specifically, it is aimed at going beyond information retrieval to do reasoning over the multimodal dataset and develop algorithms to remove the bias.

2.3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The purpose of MRI Medical Image Segmentation is to make a picture better intelligible but also simpler to examine by simplifying and/or changing its representations. Objects and boundaries (lines, curves) in images are often located via MRI Medical Image Segmentation.

2.4. METHODOLOGY:

2.4.1 The ‘kernel method’:

A variety of strong kernel-based training machines, including such Support Vector Machines, have been developed in recent years. Kernel Fisher Discriminate (KFD) [13-15]. Kernel Principal Component Analysis [17](KPCA) [16] was developed shown to be effective. Pattern classification and other uses estimate of a functional A prevalent viewpoint. The preceding is indeed the foundation for such algorithms: firstly using a kernel (substitution) technique, such that, with a from the dataset to a (implicit) nonlinear mapping $\rho : X \rightarrow F(X \rightarrow \rho(X))$, the mapping features region X (an input data space with) data $f\{x_1;x_2,x_3...x_n\} \subseteq X$ low dimension) is transferred into the a possibly considerably larger (high dimension)interior result of greater feature map, it seeks to make the nonlinear source linear. Issue in the input data into a linear problem one in a three-dimensional feature space in order toascovering [21] demonstrates, it is possible to facilitate issue resolution.

2.4.2 In the feature space, a kernel is represented by the function K:

$Ker(x,y)=\{(x), \rho(y)\}$ where $(x), \rho(y)\}$ is denoted by inner product operation. (1)

An inner combination can indeed be automatically calculated in F without explicitly utilizing or perhaps even recognizing the mapping F, which is an intriguing feature of the kernel function. As a result, kernels make it possible to compute linear combination in spaces where it would be impossible to do so otherwise. [22] are three generally used kernel functions in the literature:

(1) Kernel with a Gaussian radial basis function (GRBF):

$$ker(x,y)=\exp\left(\frac{(x-y)^2}{\sigma^2}\right) \tag{2}$$

(2) Kernel with polynomial coefficients:

$$ker(x,y)=(1+(x,y))^{d1} \tag{3}$$

(3) Kernel with a sigmoid shape:

$$ker(x,y)=\tanh(\beta(x,y)+\alpha) \tag{4}$$

These controllable variables of above kernel functions are $\alpha,\beta,d1$, and σ . Only a collection of variables matching the Mercer theorem can be utilized to build a kernel function for the sigmoid function.

2.4.3 Fuzzy C-means algorithm with kernelization

For dividing a dataset $\{x_{ker}\}_{ker=1}^N$ into c clusters, the conventional FCM goal function is:

$$S_m = \sum_{l=1}^c \sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (||x_{ker} - v_i||) \quad (5)$$

Where $\{v_{i=1}^c\}$ denotes the clusters' centers or prototypes, and u_{iker} denotes a partition matrix satisfying

$$U \in \{u_{iker} \in (0,1) \sum_{i=1}^c u_{iker} = 1\} \quad (6)$$

This parameter is a fuzzy memberships weighting exponent that influences the magnitude of fuzziness inside the resultant categorization. This gray-level value, or image pixel intensity, is by far the most widely utilized characteristic in picture clustering. Whenever strong element are assigned to pixels with intensity are near to the centric of their respective class, the FCM goal function is minimized, and so when lower element are assigned whenever the pixel is very far from the centric, the FCM optimization problem is maximized.

$$S_m = \sum_{l=1}^c \sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (||x_{ker} - \rho(v_i)||^2) \quad (7)$$

where F is an implicit nonlinear map In contrast to [19,20], $F(v_i)$ is no longer written as a linearly concatenated sum of all $F(x_k)$, such a duality representations, but instead as in the original feature space, a mapped point (picture) of v_i , which may then be solved using the kernels substitution approach. Where ρ is a nonlinear implicit map (v_i) is no longer written as a linearly concatenated sum of all, unlike [19, 20]. (x_{ker}) , such a duality representations, but instead as in the original feature space, a mapped point (picture) of v_i , which may then be solved using the kernels substitution approach.

$$||x_{ker} - \rho(v_i)||^2 = \rho(x_{ker}) - \rho(v_i) \cdot \rho(x_{ker}) - \rho(v_i) \quad (8)$$

We'll stick to the Gaussian RBF kernel in the following, so $ker(x,x)$. It's possible to simplify Equations

$$(7) \text{ and } (8) \text{ to } S_m = \sum_{l=1}^c \sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (1 - ker(x_{ker}, v_i)) \quad (9)$$

The aforementioned optimization issue is written in formal terms as

$$\min_{v_i} S_m \text{ subject to equation } (6) \quad (10)$$

This objective function S_m could be minimized there under constraints of U in a similar manner to the usual FCM technique. Furthermore, by considering that the very first derivatives of S_m with respect to u_{iker} and v_i as well as focusing them, two essential but sufficient requirements for S_m to do it at its local extreme are acquired:

$$U_{iker} = \frac{u_{iker}^N (1 - \ker(x_{ker}, v_i))}{\sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (1 - \ker(x_{ker}, v_i))} \quad (11)$$

$$v_i = \frac{\sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N \ker(x_{ker}, v_i) x_{ker}}{\sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N \ker(x_{ker}, v_i)} \quad (12)$$

For the sake of simplicity, they only employ the in the derivation of Equation. (11) and (12), a Gaussian RBF kernel was used (12), and so the algorithm in [23] is essentially a specific instance of our technique. Because the derivatives of other kernel functions [24] aren't as simple as the Gaussian RBF kernel function, for example. The associated equations are a little more complicated. A robust technique, as per Huber [24], must include following characteristics: (1) have such a reasonable level of precision in the anticipated system; (2) minor departures from the assumptions can only have a minor effect on performance a greater divergence from of the plan; and (3) a larger deviation from the model .Presumptions should not result in disaster. It has been successful. It has been demonstrated that FCM is not a reliable estimator from the statistically sound point of view [25]. According to the literature. There are a plethora of reliable estimators [26, 25]. The kernel in Eq. (2) is used in KFCM, which is a robust estimator. We can give a simple explanation for KFCM's resilience here. The data point x_{ker} is given an additional weight $\text{Ker}(x); v_i$ by Eq. (12), which measures the similarity between x_{ker} and v_i . When x_{ker} is an outlier, that is, when x_k differs significantly from the other data points, $\text{Ker}; v_i$ will be very tiny, suppressing the weighted sum of data points and making the system more robust. When s in Eq. (2) approaches zero, $\text{Ker}(x); v_i$ becomes an impulse function with a value of 1 exclusively at x_{ker} and 0 everywhere else. In this extreme instance, each data point will no longer have a neighborhood but will instead become a "solution," and the distance between any two points in the feature space will approach a common value of 1, making clustering problematic. Whenever σ approach infinity, however, the distance between these two locations in the subspace approaches 0, causing all data to cluster around, making it difficult to separate them. In fact, we should avoid such extreme circumstances by using a trial-and-error method, experience, or

foreknowledge to select a suitable sigma number that is neither too large nor too tiny. In this study, we use the trial-and-error method to select the sigma.

2.4.4 KFCM with spatial constraints for image segmentation:

Even though KFCM, like FCM, could be applied to segmentation, it's indeed useful to consider certain geographical limitations on the objective function. By incorporating comprising information about the surrounding area in space, researchers suggest a change to Eq. (7). The penalty term functions as a regularize and tends to favor piecewise-homogeneous labeling as a result, as previously stated. This type of regularization is useful for segmenting images that have been distorted by noise. The updated objectives function is calculated as follows:

$$S_m = \sum_{l=1}^C \sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N \ker(x_{ker}, v_i) \quad (13)$$

Where N_k denotes the set of neighbors in a window surrounding x_{ker} (except x_{ker} itself) and N_k 's cardinality. The duration of the penalty period effect is controlled by variable a , which ranges from zero to one inclusive. Its regularizing term's relative relevance is inversely related to the MRI information's signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Poor SNR necessitates a high a value, and conversely. Whenever the degree of membership for just a given class of pixel is large, as well as the membership functions for the cluster ought to be large at surrounding pixels, the additional penal word is minimized, and conversely. In other words, the membership value of a pixel is related to the values of the other pixels in its vicinity. This is worth noting that Eq. (13) looks remarkably like Rajesh Dave's robust fuzzy C-means proposal [25]. Furthermore, Dave's robust fuzzy C-means (see Equation (12) in [25]) and Equation (13) diverges in with at minimum two ways. To begin with, every member u_{iker} in Eq. (13) is still bound by Eq. (6), whereas in Dave's robust fuzzy C-means, the memberships are unconstrained save for the requirement that they be in $[0, 1]$. Another distinction is that in Eq. (13) we place a greater emphasis on the effect of neighbors on pixel memberships, whereas in Dave's robust fuzzy C-means there are no such neighbors.

$$u_{iker} = \frac{(1 - \ker(x_{ker}, v_i) + \beta \sum_{l=1}^C \sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (1 - u_{lir})^m)}{\sum_{ker=1}^N u_{iker}^N (1 - \ker(x_{ker}, v_i))} \quad (14)$$

Through an evaluating the cluster centers and membership functions that meet a zero gradient requirement such as the KFCM, an iterative technique for reducing Eq. (13) can be devised. The presence of a local minimum or a saddle point on u_{ik} is a necessary requirement for Eq. (13) to be true. So because penal function is independent of v_i , the essential conditions for Eq. (13) to

reach its minima are the same as for KFCM, i.e. Eq (12). Altering repetitions between both the two conditions necessary causes the algorithm to converge to the minima of Eq. (14), that is virtually identical to the KFCM, except for in Step 3(b), when Eq. (14) is used to update the members so instead Eq. (11). Designers have just discussed Gaussian RBF kernels in the foregoing discussion. In reality, we can utilize more broad RBF kernels in term of Chapelle et al. [17], as shown below:

$$\ker(x,y)=\exp(1-\gamma d_1(x,y)) \quad (15)$$

This following the general format for $d(x, y)$ could be selected.

$$d_1(x,y)=\sum_i (x_i^a - y_i^a)^2 \quad 0 < b < 2 \quad (16)$$

Clearly, the generalized RBF kernels satisfy $\ker(x,x)=1$, as well as the iteration formulas are comparable to Eq.(12) or (13) when they are utilized in Eq.(13) & (14). Contains thorough derivations of a two essential requirements for Eq. (13) being at a local minimum or a saddle point (Equation. (12) and (14) respectively).

2.5 RELATED WORK:

With the development of medical different imaging technologies, multi-modality segmentation was already extensively researched. Different picture fusion methodologies, such as Kernel with a Gaussian radial basis function (GRBF) [1][2], fuzzy membership [3], etc. 3rd concept [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11] [6] as well as machine learning [7].[8][9][10] have been created using success. Various data sets are required for methods based on GRBF and machine learning. Because modalities possess diverse intriguing features, it's complicated them with models. The fuzzy membership measure assesses the degree of uncertainty in procedures based on the fuzzy idea, membership in relation to every source's decision. These fuzzy functions are applied to a fuzzy sets for achieve the fusion of several sources. For just the belief function theory-based techniques, every resource is initially modeled by an evidentiary body, and then machine learning rule is used to fuse all of the sources together resources. The fundamental problem with using the belief function theory and fuzzy set theory is that they are both based on the belief function theory. Its evidentiary mass, fuzzy measure and fuzzy conjunction function are all options. A deep dive, on the other hand. The mapping can be directly encoded using a learning-based network. As a result, the strategy based on machine learning offers a lot of promise for producing better fusion results than traditional approaches. These models not only deliver cutting-edge performance for image classification, segmentation, object identification, and

tracking, but they also offer a fresh perspective on picture fusion. There are four primary factors that contribute to the effectiveness: To begin, advances in biological systems are the key reason for kernel zed fuzzy C-means (KFCM) incredible success over standard machine learning models; it acquires high-level features from the data in an incremental way, eliminating the requirement need subject matter expertise and laborious extraction of features. This also solves the issue from beginning to end. Second, the GPU and GPU-computing libraries have made it possible to train a model 20 to 25 times quicker than on CPUs. Furthermore, open software packages include GPU implementations that are effective. Finally, publicly available datasets like Image may be used for training, allowing researchers to test and train new machine learning versions. Furthermore, various effective optimization techniques, such as The ‘kernel method’, In the feature space, a kernel [26] is represented by the function K , and others and its variants, lead to the total success of machine. With all these, we may reach the optimal results.

2.6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Our present various experimental results in this area to evaluate the performance of several algorithms in terms of segmentation: FCM, FCM with spatial constraints (SFCM), KFCM, and KFCM [32] with spatial constraints (SKFCM) are all examples of finite element models .Using three separate datasets, we put the four techniques to the test. One would be a simple fabrication image, another is McGill University's famous simulated brain data [8], and the third is genuine MR slices. For KFCM and SKFCM, just the Gaussian RBF kernel is utilized, and in SFCM, designers just use number suggested in [30] due to the huge range of the parameter.

Fig.2.1: A simulated image with 5% Gaussian noise was used to compare segmentation results.
 (a) The original image (b) KFCM (c) (d) SKFCM and (e) FCM.

We present various results of the experiment in just this paper to evaluate the segmentation performance of the various algorithms, KFCM, due to limitations in space (SFCM), FCM, and FCM due to limitations in space (SKFCM). Using three separate datasets, researchers put the four techniques to the test. One is a simple fabrication image. Another one is McGill University's classic simulated brain database [8], as well as the third is genuine MR slices. For SKFCM and KFCM, just the RBF kernel with a Gaussian shape is utilized, and in we utilize the value recommended in [12] for SFCM. Due to the huge frequency response of the variable. Figure 1(a) depicts a synthetic image. It has a two-class pattern that has been tainted by 5% Gaussian noise. Its size of the image is 32×32 pixels, as well as the two classes have intensity levels of 0 and 80, respectively. FCM, KFCM, SFCM, and SKFCM segmentation results are shown in Figure 1(b-e), respectively. Here, $\alpha = 0.7$, $m = 2$, $NR = 8$ (a 3×3 frame centered over each pixel, save the picture value actually) are all set here. When no particular value is given, those values would be utilized throughout the rest of the article. When no specific value is given, those values will be utilized all through the rest of the article. With spatial limitations, either FCM or KFCM can distinguish the two classes, as shown in Figure 1(b) and (c), but SFCM virtually as well as SKFCM totally succeeds in rectifying and categorizing the data, shown in Figure 1(d) and (e).

Due to the obvious kernel injection, KFCM takes longer to execute than FCM, while SKFCM is faster than SFCM. Algorithms without kernel injection were usually many times better than those with kernel insertion. This synthetic test image of Figure 2(a) has been contaminated by 5% Gaussian noise plus illumination variations, which would be approximated using a sinusoid function. Overall results of FCM, KFCM, SFCM, and SKFCM are shown in Figure2 (b-e), correspondingly.

As seen in Figure 1, SKFCM gets the highest segmentation accuracy. Table 1 shows the segmentation results (SA) of four techniques in Figure 1(a) and 2(a) where the consists of different is defined as the amount of a number of pixels defined as the summation of correctly identified pixels [11].

Table 2.1: On a synthetic image, shows the segmentation accuracy (SA percent) of four approaches.

	KFCM	SKFCM	FCM	SFCM
Figure1	95.23	96.45	90.12	100
Figure2	91.23	95.34	91.34	99.98

The results of categorization using SKFCM, SFCM, KFCM, and FCM on a T1-weighted MR phantom are shown in Figures 3 and 4 [28]. Previous knowledge about true different tissues plus management over picture properties such as modalities, layer thickness, noise, and intensity in homogeneities are two advantages of employing digital phantoms instead of real picture data when testing segmentation systems. We employ a T1-weighted phantom with great resolution such a 1mm slice thickness, 3% noise, and no noise brightness non - homogeneity in our tests. Figures 3(a) and 4(a) depict two longitudinal plane slices with the sequences 91 and 121, respectively. Figures 3(b-e) and 4(b-e) illustrate the Two slices were segmented as a result of the segmentation. Employing the four approaches with eight classes, correspondingly. Table 2 shows the numerical comparative scores for the four approaches with eight classes that match to Figure 3(a) Note that while SFCM detects three classes, Class 5's score is rounded to 0.00 in Table 2 since it is too little in comparison to the other classes. The following equation [3] calculates the scores for comparison (known as a level of equality in [9]) for every algorithm and class.

Table 2.2: Compares the results of four approaches with eight classes for Figure 2.1.

	Class1	Class2	Class3	Class4	Class5	Class6	Class7	Class8
SKFCM	.45	.65	.56	.45	.45	.37	.64	.18
SFCM	.65	.85	.65	.67	.70	.87	.87	.28
KFCM	0	0	0	0	0	0	.60	.32
FCM	.64	.85	.71	.71	.70	.45	.85	.29

Where A_{ij} is the set of image pixels to a j^{th} category discovered by i^{th} algorithm, while A_{re} seems to be the collection of image pixels to a j^{th} class inside the references segmentation image.

So because roughness is fairly low, we used a 14 0:1. FCM and SFCM are unable to accurately categories the images in this scenario, however KFCM and SKFCM achieve satisfactory segmentation accuracy.

Fig.2.2: A simulated image with 5 percent Gaussian noise and sinusoidal intensity in homogeneity was used to compare segmentation results. (a) The original image (b) SKFCM(c) SFCM (d) KFCM and (e) FCM.

Fig.2.3: Comparison of segment findings on a 3 percent noise-corrupted simulated brain MR image. (a) T1-weighted original image, (b) SKFCM, (c) SFCM, (d) KFCM, and (e) FCM.

Fig.2.4: An example of simulated brain MR. (a) A 3 percent noise-corrupted T1-weighted picture, (b) Using SKFCM, (c) Using SFCM, (d) Using KFCM (e) Using FCM.

2.7 CONCLUSION

In this work, a new kernelized fuzzy C-means technique has been proposed as well as used to MR image segmentation. KFCM involves replacing Euclidean norm metric inside the data space, as well as the clustered prototype remains in the data space, allowing the clustering findings to be immediately reformulated and evaluated in the original space. A geographical restriction is introduced to KFCM's optimization problem to efficiently segment MR images that have been distorted by clutter. Despite the fact that limitation employed KFCM is comparable to it. This process is easier and it requires less computing power. Furthermore, distance produced by a Stochastic RBF is confined among exactly one and zero. Compatible with the spectrum, the value of memberships calculated based on the number of members regularizing term's relative importance by adjusting. These results obtained in this paper are tentative and much more clinical analysis is needed. Since practically most altered FCM methods for segmentation are built on introducing any type of punishment terms to the KFCM, the initial FCM objective function may be used to enhance an algorithm's performance in a relatively basic manner.

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3.1 INTRODUCTION:

Neuro-fuzzy systems have been derived from fuzzy systems that are trained with the help of a neural network-inspired learning algorithm. The fuzzy system is only modified locally by (heuristic) learning procedures, which operate on local information. It's possible to think of neuro-fuzzy systems as feed forward neural networks with three layers. The input variables are represented by the first layer, the fuzzy rules by the second layer, and the output variables by the third layer. (Fuzzy) connectivity weights represent fuzzy terms. A fuzzy system of this type does not need to be represented in order to be learned from. The model flow is used to depict the data flow of processing and learning, which might be beneficial. High-performance fuzzy systems are difficult to develop. In addition to the search of membership functions and appropriate rules, which is often error-prone, there are several other challenges [1]. Thus, fuzzy systems were also treated with the learning algorithms. A fuzzy system could also be automated by using neural networks [2]. In addition to their use in process control applications, neural networks can also be used to analyze data, classify data, detect imperfections, and support decision-making. To increase their advantages and to eliminate their shortcomings, neural networks and fuzzy systems can be combined. Neural network learning techniques can be used to accelerate the creation of fuzzy systems, lower their costs, and increase their performance [3]. The Figures 1 and 2 demonstrate two possible fuzzy neural network models. A multilayer neural network is triggered by linguistic statements by a fuzzy interface block (Figure 1). Taking into account a multi-layered neural network representation, fuzzy inference is determined in the Figure 2, Rule based Cooperative fuzzy neural network system is determined in the figure 3. Image assisted radiotherapy, image assisted surgery, image approach to solving therapy, and advanced imaging navigation are all quite popular right now. It encourages medical imaging technology research and development [4-5]. Compared to traditional surgical procedures, image-guided surgery is much more accurate and efficient, and can reduce surgical risks. Image segmentation technology is essential for guiding surgery with images.

Fig.3.1: Neuron model based on fuzzy logic

Fig.3.2: Fuzzy Neuron model

Fig.3.3: Cooperative fuzzy neural network

In image-guided surgery, the benefits and drawbacks of segmentation are critical. [6-8]. Medical image analysis is a growing field, where segmenting medical images is a complicated and critical step. By using this type of diagram, the area of anatomical interest or a certain tissue can be depicted with the greatest degree of accuracy. Various methods exist for segmenting medical images. Machine learning and deep learning are the two main categories of medical image segmentation methods [9-12]. Artificial intelligence applications have focused much attention on deep learning [13-14] in recent years. Its precision has substantially improved a range of applications. The aforesaid issues can be handled.

It is difficult to model certain data modalities using shallow models for the methods based on probabilistic theory and machine learning because they have different statistical properties. Fuzzy measurements estimate the degree of membership associated to a judgment for each source in methods based on the fuzzy principle. When fuzzy operators are applied to fuzzy sets, several sources are merged together. The Dempster Shafer rule is used to fuse all source models based on the belief function theory, and then each source is modeled by an evidentiary mass. The decision should not be taken until the evidentiary mass, the fuzzy measure, and the fuzzy conjunction function have been calculated in order to apply the belief function theory and the fuzzy set theory.

3.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Medical image acquisition systems [36] have been extensively used studied for improving accuracy of multi-modal segmentation. Image fusion can be achieved using many different strategies, including probability theory, fuzzy concepts, believe functions and machine learning. A better medical picture segmentation method based on deep learning has to be worked out for analyzing the network topology of the deep learning model and add cross-layer connections to the standard CNN. The mapping can be directly encoded by a deep learning-based network. As a result, utilizing deep learning to produce better fusions has a huge amount of potential and improves the segmentation accuracy.

3.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

This research paper has covered information related to various existing FCM algorithms for MRI of medical image segmentation. This research work is carried out with the following broad objectives.

- To study the existing algorithm.
- To analyze the data related to the intensity levels of the existing KFCM-CA Algorithm.
- To identify the advantages, disadvantages and issues if any with existing algorithm.
- To propose the KFCM with clustering Algorithm for Neuro fuzzy based Concept using for MRI Medical Image Segmentation.
- To identify the improvement of classification, number of iterations.

3.4 METHODOLOGY:

3.4.1 K-Means Algorithm

In general, K-Means algorithms [28] are quite fast. The system is easy to understand and robust. Clustering is one of the most well known problems, K-means solves that problem effectively and it is an unsupervised learning algorithm. Using a certain number of clusters that are fixed a priori, a given data set is categorized as easily as possible. There are k centroids for each cluster, which is the concept. Because the results from different locations are different, these centroids must be placed in a clever manner. In other words, placing them as far away from one another as possible is the better option. The following step entails choosing a centroid for each point in a given data set. The first step is complete when no pending points exist, and an early grouping is done. As a result of the previous step, we need to recalculate k new centroids as bar centers of the clusters. After acquiring these k new centroids, a fresh binding must be conducted to bind the identical points to the nearest new centroid. Thus we have generated a loop. This loop would cause the k centroids to move around in their location until no more changes are made. To put it differently, centroids stop moving. This algorithm's main goal is to minimize a squared error function. The objective function is given by.

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^m \|x_j^i - C_i\|^2$$

3.4.2 Clustering Algorithm using Fuzzy C Means (FCM)

Among the most classical and traditional image segmentation algorithms [31] is fuzzy c-means (FCM). An objective function is minimized by using an FCM algorithm. A dataset is partitioned into c clusters according to the objective function. A weighted squared error objective function is

minimized by employing an iterative clustering algorithm to determine an optimal cell partition. The fuzzy c-means (FCM) clusters data by allowing one piece of information to be considered. Pattern recognition usually entails using this method. The following objective function can be used to minimize the FCM algorithm [33].

$$F_m = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^m u_{ij}^n \|x_j - c_i\|^2$$

In a cluster, n represents the real number of members, u_{ij} represents the degree of membership, and c_i indicates the cluster's center in d -dimensions.

$$U_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{l=1}^c \left(\frac{\|x_j - c_l\|}{\|x_j - c_i\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{n-1}}}$$

$$C_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k U_{ij}^n x_j}{\sum_{i=1}^k U_{ij}^n}$$

For overlapped data sets, FCM provides the best results. In comparison with K-means, it is more accurate. The k-means algorithm requires that data points belong to only one cluster centre. Data points are allocated membership to each cluster centre as a result, and they can belong to many cluster centres. The number of clusters must be specified a priori.

3.4.3 Kernel Fuzzy C means cellular automata (KFCM-CA)

Kernel Fuzzy C Means cellular automata (KFCM-CA) Kernel information is added to the classic fuzzy c-means technique [42] with the KFCM-CA algorithm. The KFCM-CA algorithm also addresses the problem that it is unable to account for small differences between clusters in FCM algorithms. Kernel methods map the input data space into the input data space nonlinearly, resulting in a high-dimensional feature space. As the name implies, kernel-based methods operate by performing a non-linear mapping from the originally d -dimensional feature space to a higher dimensional space (kernel space). There is no limit to the size of kernel space. Taking the problem to higher dimensions may allow a linear classifier to be applied in the kernel space, although the original problem in the feature space may be very non-linear and difficult to separate using linear methods. This method functions by taking advantage of the fact that Mercer

kernels can be used to represent dot products in the kernel space. The distance in the kernel space does not need to be determined explicitly because Mercer kernel functions can replace the distance computation.

As an alternative to the original squared-norm distance metric, the algorithm uses a kernel-induced distance metric. With this kernel version, we may modify the FCM algorithm's objective function [43] as follows

$$F_n = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^N u_{ij}^n \|f(x_j) - f(y_i)\|^2$$

$$\text{Where, } \|f(x_j) - f(y_i)\|^2 = Z(x_j, x_j) + Z(y_i, y_i) - 2Z(x_j, y_i)$$

$$\text{So, } F_n = 2 \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^N u_{ij}^n [1 - Z(x_j, y_i)]$$

$$\text{Where, } u_{ij} = \frac{[1 - Z(x_j, y_i)]^{-1}}{\sum_{i=1}^c [1 - Z(x_j, y_i)]^{-1}} \text{ and}$$

$$y_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N u_{ij}^n Z(x_j, y_i) x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N u_{ij}^n Z(x_j, y_i)}$$

3.4.4 CNNs Modeling Optimization

The optimized CNN model architecture includes a fully connected layer, a convolution layer, pooling layer, an interleaved convolution layer, and an output layer. In Figure 4, we see how layers of convolution are combined with layers of pooling in a cross-layer connection to produce a fully connected layer.

Fig.3.4: Splicing a CNN.

Consider there are 3 spatial dimensions to the input X are H, W, and n (H*W*n); channel dimension is n; color images are represented when n=2 , and n = 1 representing grayscale images. F denotes the activation function. Following are the calculations for the convolution layer:

$$H_{2m-1,i}^1 = C_{m,i}^1 = F(u_{2m-1,j}^1) = F\left[\sum_j H_{2m-1,j}^1 * W_{ji}^{2m-1} + B_i^{2m-1}\right]$$

The step size of all feature faces in a pooled layer is fixed. In this case, pooling [*] can be average or maximum. We can define the pooling function as follows:

$$H_{2m,i}^1 = t_{m,i}^1 = pooling(H_{2m-1,i}^1)$$

Layers are connected through a cross-layer connection when two or more convolution layers are activated along with a pooled layer. Several fully connected layers can constitute a multi scale feature discriminate vector. It can be represented as follows:

$$H_{2s+1}^1 = [s_1 h_1^1, s_2 h_2^1, \dots, s_{2s} H_{2s}^1], \quad \text{here binary string } S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2s-1}\}$$

3.4.5 Designs based on adaptive distribution functions

Adaptive distribution functions are employed in this study to mask the layer's position as an independent variable and the layer's activation probability as a dependent variable. Each hidden layer is given a probability of activation, which is set by its position. The adaptive distribution function lowers monotonically as the hidden layer position increases, according to this investigation. [15-16] . According to Hinton's dropout model, neurons in each layer should have an activation probability of about 0.5. The goal is to maintain enough active neurons.

Furthermore, the depth calculation model is discarded enough neurons to make it suitable for generalization. As a final measure, the dropout rate of each layer should lie anywhere between 0 and 1. In this paper, we propose the following adaptive distribution function:

$$\rho = f(x) = \left[\begin{array}{l} 1 - \frac{1}{\tau\sqrt{2\Pi}} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-\frac{(1-m/2)^2}{2\tau^2}} dx \\ 1 - \frac{1}{\tau\sqrt{2\Pi}} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-\frac{[x-(1+m/2)]^2}{2\tau^2}} dx \end{array} \right]$$

With x indicating the hidden layer's location, m indicating the depth calculation model's number of layers, and r indicating the dropout rate range control parameter.

3.4.6 An efficient CNN approach for estimating dropout depths – Image segmentation

Based on sections 4.4 and 4.5 of the paper, this section proposes an adaptive drop-out depth calculation method for CNNs used to segment medical images. By adding cross-layer connections into a normal CNN, an optimized CNN model is generated. This solution will allow deep learning models to be flexible with their network structure. Similarly, this study proposes an adaptive dropout model that will increase the generalizability of the dropout strategy while reducing deep learning complexity. Based on the medical image segmentation technique [43] that employs a CNN with adaptive drop out depth calculation. This algorithm is depicted in Figure 5 as a basic idea. it consists of the following steps:

1. The first step is to denoise, add, and expand the data in the medical images.
2. The second step is to propose a new optimized CNN model that extends traditional CNNs with cross-layer connections and thus significantly improves network structure of deep learning models. By using two scale features simultaneously in an optimized CNN model, it is possible to better segment medical images.
3. The third step is to propose the activation probability of each layer of neurons is set up using an adaptive distribution function based on the location of each hidden layer, improving the generalizability of the dropout model even further. Thus, the general dropout method of deep learning is no longer applicable, reducing generalizability. The deep learning model can be made more generalizable and the over fitting risk reduced.
4. In steps (1)–(3), the goal of medical image segmentation is met by integrating the method of step (3) with the method of step (2). This leads to a segmentation algorithm that relies on an

optimization of CNNs with adaptive dropout depth calculations. Analyzing related examples, comparing and analyzing with mainstream methods of segmenting medical images is the objective of this algorithm.

3.4.7 A Model of Weighed Level Sets

Because of noise and bias fields, many existing algorithms are unable to correctly segment brain MRI images. The problem of local multiple-information is addressed by combining a weighted level set model with local multiple-information. Using kernel metrics and fuzzy spatial membership limits, the approach allows for accurate segmentation of brain MRI images. The neighborhood information of the central pixel y_i , which was most successful on pictures of low-contrast brain MRI, where white matter and grey matter are intermingled and the line between them is indistinct, was used to improve image quality in this paper. Local variation, spatial distance, and gray-level difference are all employed simultaneously for the weighted neighborhood information, which will be explored separately in this part. Variation occurs in the local window of y_i based on the pixel intensity mean and variance. Pixels can be related to each other intuitively by variance, which is defined as deviation from the mean. The set of neighbor pixels y_j surrounding the center pixel y_i is represented by the coefficients C_{ij} , where C_{ij} represents the local variation coefficient:

$$C_{ij} = \frac{\text{Variance}[y_j]}{[\bar{y}_j]^2}$$

Due to its computational simplicity, Euclidean distance continues to be used in some traditional studies. If noise, inhomogeneity in intensity, and other effects destroy the images, Euclidean distance will be difficult or impossible to measure accurately. Hence, we construct a nonlinear distance metric that improves Euclidean distance by using kernel metrics. The fuzzy spatial C-means [42] and support vector clustering [44] have been developed utilizing this technique. An efficient distance measure is the Gaussian kernel function, which is defined as:

$$D_{ij}^2 = e^{\left[\frac{-\|y_j - y_i\|^2}{\sigma} \right]}$$

3.5 RELATED WORK

The development of various semi-automated and automated methods, such as CNN [19] and FCN [17] as well as U-Net [18], has been explored for multi-modal medical image segmentation over the years.

Fig.3.5: Classification of the fusion strategy

3.5.1 Input-level fusion network

Fusion of multi-modality images at the input level involves fusing images channel by channel to learn a merged feature representation, and then training the segmentation network using the merged representation. A majority of existing multimodal medical image segmentation networks apply the input-level fusion technique to integrate these images directly into the original input space [20-24]. An input-level fusion segmentation network is shown in figure 7. Using CT and MRI as inputs, CNN as segmentation network, and brain tumor segmentation to perform the segmentation task, we use CT and MRI to segment brain tumors. A multilevel fusion strategy can fully utilize the rich feature information in all layers, from the first layer to the last layer, in order to exploit the rich feature information from different modalities. It is possible to maximize the preservation and learning of original image information using the input-level fusion strategy. Sequentially segmenting images with sequential segmentation networks generates many different strategies, such as multitasking, multi-viewing, multi-scale, and GAN-based segmentation networks, for fully exploiting the features found in multi-modal images.

Fig.3.6: Network architecture of the input-level fusion

3.5.2 Layer-level fusion

To train individual segmentation networks using the layer-level fusion strategy, only one or two modal images are used as inputs. Following that, the layers of the network will fuse these learned individual feature representations. A final segmentation result will be obtained by feeding the fused results into the decision layer. Multi-modal images can be effectively integrated and fully leveraged by the layer-level fusion network [26-28]. Layer-level fusion segmentation works are shown in Figure 8.

Fig.3.7: Network architecture of the layer-level fusion

3.5.3. Decision-level fusion

In a single segmentation network composed of decision-level fusion segmentation, each modality image contains one input. By combining the individual networks, the unique features of each can be more efficiently exploited. Finally, the segmentation result will be generated by integrating the resulting outputs of the individual networks. Since multimodal images usually contain little complementary information due to different acquisition techniques, they tend to have fewer direct complementarities. In decision-level fusion segmentation, information from different sources is independently learned in different modes. Layer-level fusion segmentation work is illustrated in Figure 9 as generic network architecture.

Fig.3.8: Network architecture of the decision-level fusion

3.6 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

KFCM-CA used to segment realistic and synthetic images of MRI and compares them to state-of-the-art models. In the first step, it enhances the quality of MRI images by using the weighted neighborhood information within Weighted Level Set Model (WLSM). This will improve the segmentation accuracy (SA) of MRI images with varying degrees of noise. MRI images with inhomogeneous intensities are corrected using this method and the bias field is estimated as well. Finally, the KFCM-CA segmentation method is tested on sagittal, coronal and axial slices of synthetic and actual MRI images to demonstrate its performance. An MRI simulator produces simulated brain MR images that are close to actual brain MRI images. This is known as Brain Web, a simulated brain database. The Montreal Neurology Institute developed it as part of its brain imaging center. A three-dimensional matrix is used to represent the brain MR images shown in figure 10. The original images in the first column were ruined by noise, as can be seen in the somewhat expanded regions denoted by green rectangles, notably in areas where WM and GM are intertwined. By comparison, the improved images in the second column, which use weighted neighborhood information, are more noise free than original images and allow clear demarcation of the boundaries between tissues. For purposes of updating the central pixel, Weighted Level Set Model uses local variation, spatial distances and gray-level information obtained from the neighbors of the central pixel. In a given tissue, pixels that are adjacent in weight will have a larger weight, and vice versa. Pixels in the weak borders can subsequently be classified into the respective tissues based on their weighted neighbor information.

To demonstrate WLSM's performance, the experiment of this subsection uses MRI images of the brain with a noise of 3% and different degrees of intensity in homogeneity to segment them. Figure 11 shows pictures with 3% noise as well as 60%, 80%, and 100% intensity in homogeneity. As illustrated in the corrected and segmented images in the second column,

without being impacted by noise or intensity in homogeneity, WLSM can be used to correct inhomogeneous intensity and segment images at the same time. The segmentation results in the third column are the same whether the inhomogeneous intensity is lower or higher, WLSM's ability to simultaneously correct inhomogeneous intensity and segment pictures without affecting noise and intensity in homogeneity is demonstrated.

Fig.3.9:Images of the brain segmented by WLSM; (a).Original Image (b).Improved image (c).Segmentation (d).Classified image

Fig.3.10 : (a) Original image (b) Corrected image (c) Segmentation

3.7. CONCLUSION:

In this research paper, noise-affected MR images were segmented using a novel method. Based on the kernel method, the algorithm is simple to understand. In this algorithm, the distance metric is introduced into the objective function as a kernel-induced modification of conventional fuzzy c-means. In terms of spatial penalty, neighboring pixels have an influence on the central pixel. To construct a better medical picture segmentation method based on deep learning, it is first proposed to analyze the network topology of the deep learning model and add cross-layer connections to the standard CNN. This model is optimized using CNNs. CNNs can segment images using two scale features simultaneously. Because both noise and intensity inhomogeneity frequently damage MRI images, the model's ability to adjust inhomogeneous intensity and estimate bias field is crucial.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS IN INTERNATIONAL JOURNALS

1. Dr.Nookala Venu and Dr.Rajanna G.S, “Integration of HGFCM Algorithm for Nero fuzzy based Concept using for MRI Medical Image Segmentation.”, High Technology Letters (HTL), ISSN: 1006-6748, Volume 28, Issue 6, June-2022, PP: 479-483.
2. Dr.Nookala Venu and Dr.Rajanna G.S, “Performance analysis of various FCM algorithms for Neuro fuzzy Based Concept using for MRI Medical Image Segmentation.”, GIS Science Journal, Volume 9, Issue 6, ISSN: 1869-9391, June-2022, PP: 1764-1777.
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